

Kühn, I., Ambrosi, V. & Kaune, P. (2023). Women in information and communication technology: Creating opportunities for career changers towards IT and IT-mixed professions. In V. Tütlys, L. Vaitkutė & C. Nägele (Eds.), *Vocational Education and Training Transformations for Digital, Sustainable and Socially Fair Future. Proceedings of the 5th Crossing Boundaries Conference in Vocational Education and Training, Kaunas, 25. – 26. May* (pp. 245–252). European Research Network on Vocational Education and Training, VETNET, Vytautas Magnus University Education Academy, Institute of Educational Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7821871>

Women in Information and Communication Technology: Creating Opportunities for Career Changers Towards IT and IT-Mixed Professions

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Abstract

Context: Women are underrepresented in IT at all professional levels. This fact stands contrary to the growing capacity shortage within the whole sector. Different factors hinder women to enter IT professions, such as a lack of qualification, care and family tasks or a kind of clichés that hinder the industry being attractive. A high percentage of part-time employments or a significant gender-pay gap are one aspect of the disadvantage, another comes from missing digital-confidence and, through that, a lack of participation opportunities for women. A way to challenge the future skills shortage is to encourage and enable marginalised women to take up careers in the IT sector. This research aims to identify relevant factors that support this process.

Approach: In focus groups with IT companies and regional employment agencies were carried out. Moreover, women from the target group at two different stages of professional development were inquired. The data was analysed following the social area approach in order to identify relevant factors in the living and potential learning environment of the target group.

Findings: Results show a number of hindering factors, such as a lack of structures within companies or public organisations to either professionally involve newbies in IT or counselling for women interested in the sector. Women are both, afraid of and highly engaged in trying. Other promising factors are the will of companies to involve more women and the readiness of public bodies to contribute.

Conclusions: Solutions to reach more women for IT can be seen in creating networks including economic and public sector, organised exchange, expansion of counselling and specific transition education offers and transparency of pathways and joint promotion campaigns. The research is limited by a small sample.

Keywords

women in IT, IT sector, vocational education and training, continuing vocational education and training, social area, career changing

1 Problem statement and research question

The global Information and Communication Technology (ICT¹) sector is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 6 % until 2026 (GlobalData, 2022). Despite the stable growth of the sector, its biggest challenge is the current and future lack of skilled workers (Bayer et al., 2022). Until 2030, a growing need for professionals is predicted especially in the industry 4.0 sector (Hall et al., 2016) and the field of Software as a Service (SaaS) (GlobalData, 2022). In Germany, half of the population has only basic digital skills (54 % in 2021; *ibid.*). Furthermore, a continuous underrepresentation of women in the IT sector is reported, not only for the German context (Spieler & Both, 2021), but worldwide (UNESCO, 2017).

Following Friemer & Warsewa (2020), the number of women in the IT sector stagnates at around 28% in the region of Bremen, Germany. They find that companies have difficulties to fill vacancies for IT specialists, while there is enough specialised training in the region (Friemer & Warsewa, 2020). Apart from that, women face a lot of disadvantages related to the labour market, such as the substantial gender pay gap (Hall et al., 2016; Chamber of Employees, 2022a) or, for the region of Bremen, high rates of part-time employments (about 74%; Chamber of Employees, 2022b; Brück-Klingeberg & Althoff, 2019).

This raises the question of reasons for and solutions towards a reduction of the mentioned underrepresentation. Research led by Spieler and Both (2021) indicates various motivations for women in Western cultures not to choose a career in IT, such as a lack of qualification, care and family tasks or a kind of cliché that prevents the industry from being perceived as attractive (Spieler & Both 2021). Moreover, the European Institute for Gender Equality in Lithuania (EIGE) reports that a lack of digital-confidence is a major barrier to the use of IT (EIGE, 2019). Another approach describes the character of the IT sector as excluding women through male-dominated re-construction mechanisms, which would contribute to a highly gender-specific view of problems to be solved (Maier-Rabler, 2022).

Former research on the transition of women into the IT sector was conducted e.g., by Ahuja (2002). She identified certain factors relevant at different levels of career stages and differs social and structural factors affecting women's careers in IT. Social factors, in her understanding, are the internal and external view of women problematising stereotypes on the one hand and, as a result, self-selection based on gender bias, which leads women into gender-typed professions (Ahuja, 2002). Structural factors are described as the limitations created by organisations. Hampering factors are work place conditions that do not fit the life reality of women, especially with family duties (e.g., long travels or working days and permanent continuing training). A lack of role models and mentors are also seen as part of structural factors. Ahuja identifies approaches to enhance the situation of women towards IT in the reduction of stereotypes, flexibilization of work structures, the critically reflected use of power at higher positions could enhance career aspirations. Moreover, role models and mentoring programs are mentioned as promising.

Other approaches come from Latin America. García-Holgado et al. (2016) aim to attract women for the IT sector by improving the processes of attraction, access and guidance in relevant programs (García-Holgado et al., 2016). In the focus of their research is the measurement of gender equality in Science Technology Engineering Mathematics (STEM) programs.

Informatics Europe (2016), a cross-national working group at European level, provides practical guidelines to engage women for IT by addressing and promoting them in a particular

¹ The Information Technology (IT) and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) are different by scope, which is not always reflected in literature. The F.IT project refers to the local IT-sector, accordingly, the abbreviation IT is used for this research.

way (Bujdosó, 2016). Though the mentioned studies can only give an impression of the discourse, it seems that research in this field is limited from different perspectives: firstly, most of the studies focus on women at high professional level with academic perspective. Secondly, it shows that there is no overarching, generally effective solution so far, which is why research projects are likely to start with a direct regional reference. A third limitation appears to be the discussion of disadvantaged women mainly at the level of lacking social participation in everyday life, but not with direct regard to their potential for the local labour markets.

It is striking that the limited debate excludes the perspective of disadvantaged groups such as women without academic degrees. Therefore, the project “F.IT Frauen in IT [Women in IT]”² (duration: 09/2020–12/2023) focuses on this target group and their potential in the IT industry in Bremen. An important part of the project’s research is presented here and is informed by the following two research questions: *What factors within a social area would enable the specific group of women without academic degrees to enter the IT sector? What does that mean for the creation of specific (VET) offerings aimed at women to entering the IT-sector?*

2 Theoretical Framework

For this research, it is important to emphasize that equality does not mean gender neutrality (Noll, 2020). This respects the specific perception of women concerning the value and occupational opportunities of IT in relation to their individual perspective. Furthermore, the debate often focuses on female STEM and IT professionals, thereby excluding the perspective of vulnerable groups, such as women without academic degree. By focusing on this target group and their potential in the IT industry, the F.IT project aims to enrich the discourse.

In order to understand, why some women choose a career in IT and why others do not, it is therefore necessary to reconstruct the conditions and environments these women live in. The study is based on the social area orientation approach (Fleige, 2013; Mania, 2021) that aims to improve the addressing of allegedly educationally disadvantaged groups (Mania, 2021). To identify challenges and opportunities of all actors, it respects traditional dimensions of program planning at the regional level (Fleige, 2013) and relates dimensions of the social orientation with those of the social area (Mania, 2021), termed the SONI-approach (Früchtel et al., 2010).

² The project is funded by the Senator for Economic Affairs, Labour and Europe Bremen, co-financed by the European Union.

Figure 1

Integrated categories of the social area orientation approach (own presentation, following Fleige 2013 and Mania, 2021)

Relevant for this paper are the categories “social structure” (S), “organisation” (O), “network” (N) and “individual” (I). Figure 1 visualizes the structure of the theoretical frame. This approach helps to systematically structure different perspectives on a social area to identify conducive conditions that support women enter the IT sector. The *social structure* (S) addresses the societal frame as a structure for empowerment that illuminates the structural origins of problems and inequalities. The *perspective of organisation* (O) highlights organisational structures, internal processes and professional self-conception. The *network dimension* (N) picks up the topic of resources and opportunities of the social area and the potentials of the inherent social capital. The *individual level* (I), finally, comprises individual factors, such as interest, experiences, attitudes, expectations or life situation (Mania, 2021).

The program planning level approach targets the identification of the educational interests present in a geographically delineated space and how they can be stimulated through the development of the (physical) learning environments. Mutual search movements between (educational) institutions and potential learners aim participation. The systematic analysis of the social area of a region is the base for the development of future learning activities. These efforts specially focus groups at risk of exclusion (Fleige, 2013). The dimensions lifeworld (social cultural factors), learning venue (learning location), learning portal (participation through fitting education offers) and learning culture (institutional embedding of education offers) describe specific elements of how the specific conditions of a region can be applied to control the development of education offers (ibid.).

In the context of this study, the target group consists of women assumed to be disadvantaged against the background of an industry because they do not have an academic degree and, if they are older, may have a higher effort to balance professional development and family or care responsibilities. This paper focuses on the dimensions of SONI. The program development approach, within this context, serves to classify the results by the evaluation of local conditions for the potential learning environment.

3 Methods

This study employs a combination of focus groups with experts (Tausch & Menold, 2015) and descriptive quantitative inquiries of women interested in working in the IT sector (Döring & Bortz, 2016).

Experts within this study are representatives of IT companies (n=4; WS1), from public institutions with an administrative mandate and from a local VET and counselling agency (n=7; WS2). From the side of the target group, women from two different educational courses participated in the study, coming from either an IT orientation course or from an occupation course in the field of IT at a vocational school. Women in the first group were aged between 30 and >60 years (n=25) and in the second group between <18 and 28 years (n=12). The two groups of women answered two different online questionnaires aiming to identify specific life circumstances and motivational factors concerning their professional orientation. Women participating in the orientation course answered questions regarding their former career and job ambitions (OS1), while those at the VET school were asked about their worries and coping approaches during the decision process (OS2). Surveyed companies were asked about the requirements needed to enter the IT sector (WS1). The local public entities discussed possibilities to address more women interested in IT (WS2). Both focus groups were documented in detail. In order to scrutinize the findings from the online surveys, two currently career changing women (I1; I2) were interviewed during their internships, as well as their (male) internship supervisors (I3; I4). For this analysis, the first two interview documentations are used.

4 Results and discussion

The first research question aims to identify *factors within a specific environment that would enable the women without academic degrees to enter the ICT-sector*. Selected results are presented according to the theoretical frame of the social area approach (Mania, 2021).

Findings regarding the *social structure* (S) of the region show a lack of transparency towards existing opportunities for women to move into IT or IT-related fields. Classic career paths dominate entry procedures (WS1). The regional employment agency as a public player seems to be an important door opener when it comes to attracting women to the IT sector (or not), provided that the women present themselves to the employment agency at all (WS2). Women state that local options are not visible enough. They rather come to offers through their own research work and after a long odyssey of search and decision-making processes (I1; I2; OS2).

Results for the *organisation perspective* (O) are that the external image of IT companies is very much based on the fact that people take advantage of (training) offerings on their own initiative and strive independently for individual professionalisation processes (entry by own engagement, OS1; OS2). If there is little or no prior experience, companies prefer apprentices over internships because they can get a better return for their efforts (WS1). If individuals do not come across opportunities in IT on their own initiative, counselling through the regional employment agency is an option (WS2; OS1). The agency is able to provide financial support for continuing education in IT. Among others factors, these efforts are limited by the potential in identifying interested women for continuing education courses or companies. Companies describe trainees that aim at a career change as highly engaged, but not sufficiently qualified for being integrated directly into ongoing project work. They require a rather focused than broad qualification (I3; I4). Overall, the sector reports a high interest of including women (WS1; I3).

For the *network dimension* (N), the attitude of the companies with regard to the design of employee-friendly workplaces, as well as numerous ideas for designing a possible entry via internships (WS1), indicate that the industry is open to future professionals, also from the target group of female career changers without academic degree. Moreover, the landscape of professionalization offers consists of a multitude of education providers within the field (WS2). Interviewed women mentioned an improvement of cooperation between public authorities (e.g., coordination between parental allowance office and employment agency; OS1) or a more direct approach by the companies desirable (OS2).

Finally, results at *individual level* (I) show that companies expect prior knowledge from their applicants (WS1; I3; I4). Additionally, they are concerned that women changing their careers at a later point in life feel under pressure and, thereby, challenge the “social aspects” of a company, e.g., by demanding special work-life-balance offerings (WS1). Women interested in IT report both, a certain fear of having worse chances on the labour market if they do not change careers and the fear of not being able to meet the requirements for apprenticeships or further education (OS2). However, they state that open-mindedness and empowerment help to motivate themselves (OS1; I1; I2). Technical experience in the past appears helpful in this regard (I1; I2). Remarkable is the often-negative association of further education with pressure from public administration authorities.

The results lead to a number of factors relevant to enabling women without academic degree to enter the IT sector. IT companies could *change their hiring strategies*, e.g., towards more qualified entry-level offers. Moreover, they are obliged to *clearly formulate the requirements* for future employees and, for example, to allow informally acquired skills to be tested in practice. Both approaches would contribute to a visibility at a lower level. In addition, it seems promising to implement internal structures or external cooperation to create *supporting structures* for IT beginners. A *clear statement on gender equality* or work-life-balance could attract those with care duties.

As a key-player between target group and IT-sector, the regional employment agency might adapt resp. extend its *advisory services* to draw women’s attention to the IT sector. The provided financial support must ensure that female candidates do not experience any blatant cuts in their quality of life.

The greatest assets of women who want to enter the IT sector is their *willingness to learn* as well as their *motivation*. They report self-confidence in dealing with their fears about their future and the demands of a job in IT.

The second research question asks for concrete VET offerings to support women to enter IT. It is noted that the synchronization of companies and local employment agencies is a challenging, but necessary task. This could be supported by VET through the creation of sustainable networks (including suitable formats of exchange) with low-threshold access for the target group. Regarding the women’s situation, especially CVET offers focusing on empowerment and sector-related knowledge might also be helpful. To reach more interested women, an inviting and area-wide joint promotion campaign of all actors from economy, public administration and VET appears promising.

5 Conclusion

This study identified the following factors enabling women without academic degrees to enter the ICT sector: (1) transparency of job requirements, (2) transparency of career pathways provided by all network actors, (3) a differentiated and sensitizing range of consulting services in public institutions, (4) creation of a work-life-balance not only in work contexts, but also in qualification processes and, finally, (5) appreciation of the women’s motivation and their willingness to learn as social capital. These factors can be accompanied by specific efforts at the program planning level, such as the creation of sustainable networks including formats of exchange, the creation of (C)VET offers that empower women to apply for the IT-sector and a joint, overarching public relation campaign.

Limitations are given by small sample sizes, the use of protocols as the data basis, the lack of availability of participants for interviews and workshops and the difficulties in finding women willing to enter IT.

Future research might aim to validate the presented results by enlarging the sample of women or by targeting nationwide federal employment agencies or enterprises in contrast to only locally operating agents. In addition to that, the importance of education and counselling

providers who serve as a link between women, public bodies and companies, could be examined. The development of supporting education offers in the region might be a research subject at program planning level. Finally, general and specific job requirements could be surveyed, e.g., through needs and work process analyses. Overall, continuing research on women's pathways in IT is needed, since it seems that there is not that one solution for the problem, but a number of solutions for different compositions of conditions.

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